

THE EXTENT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF PROJECT INSPIRE (INTENSIFYING NURTURING SUPERVISORY PARTNERSHIP OF INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERS FOR RELEVANCE AND EXCELLENCE) IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF CAUAYAN CITY: A BASIS FOR CONTINUAL IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of Project INSPIRE in the Schools Division of Cauayan City which served as a basis for continual improvement. All school heads of 79 elementary and secondary schools in SDO Cauayan City were considered as respondents. The 253 Elementary Teachers, 109 Senior High School Teachers, and 193 Junior High School Teachers also served as respondents of the study chosen through stratified random sampling. To facilitate the collection of data, survey questionnaire and interview/focus group discussion were utilized. The researcher utilized frequency and percentage distribution, mean rating, t-test, ANOVA, and coding and thematic analysis in treating the data gathered. The findings revealed that Project INSPIRE and the instructional supervision of both Education Program Supervisors (EPS) and School Heads are implemented to a very great extent. Significant differences were found in the instructional supervision of EPS when school heads were grouped by years in service, and in the instructional supervision of School Heads when teachers were grouped by position and years in service. The key challenges in implementing Project INSPIRE include the Covid-19 pandemic, multiple responsibilities of school heads, qualifications and capacity issues, unequal opportunities for teachers, and teacher attitudes toward supervision. Its strengths include intensified supervision, enhanced instructional leadership, strengthened partnerships, effective management of instructional programs, and improved learning management. Based on these findings, it

is recommended that school heads continue strengthening instructional supervision and that instructional leaders maintain effective supervisory practices and support ongoing staff development to improve teaching performance.

Keywords: *extent of implementation, instructional supervision, supervisory partnership, improvement*

INTRODUCTION

Intensifying supervision of instruction is one of the most critical functions of Education Program Supervisors, Public Schools District Supervisors and School Heads as instructional leaders since student learning is the primordial concern of the department. Additionally, nurturing instructional leaders is integral to every school success, teacher quality, and student achievement. Supervisory skills in planning, monitoring, conferencing and analyzing performance and appropriate data on instructional supervision in a coordinated and collaborative manner, instructional leaders and supervisors can provide meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that can have a profound effect on the learning that occurs in each classroom.

Partnership is where quality delivery of instruction is largely dependent. Hence, strengthening school-community relationship becomes of utmost importance for a long term and sustainable nation building. Recognizing the crucial role of community in addressing the challenge of quality education, the Department of Education included engaging partnership as one of the quadrants of kite, the official logo of the Sulong Edukalidad.

Quality of instruction is the top priority for the instructional landscapers. Instructional leadership is committed to the core business of teaching, learning, and knowledge. Relevance and meaningfulness of instruction shall be the primordial concern of the supervisors and school heads in creating opportunities for learning. Excellence is going beyond the minimum standard. This project aims at offering curricula responsive to the uniqueness of learner excellently; providing them the appropriate learning opportunities and options amid meagre resources; networking with the civic-spirited stakeholders and community people for a sustainable support beyond expectation; and provision of avenue for teachers' up skilling and reskilling for content, pedagogy and technical aspects more than the minimum standards.

The rapid changes brought about by the global and national frameworks such as the K to 12 Reform, ASEAN Integration, globalization and the changing character of the 21st century learners necessitate the improvements and call for the rethinking of the National Competency-Based, Teacher Standards (NCBTS), hence the issuance of DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, the Philippine Professional Standards for teachers (PPST).

In 2015, the DepEd issued Order No. 2, s. 2015 – “Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) in

the Department of Education” following Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 06, s. 2012 of the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) to ensure efficient, timely, and quality performance among personnel. The guidelines explains mechanism, criteria and processes for performance target setting, monitoring, evaluation and development planning. This RPMS needs to be aligned with the PPST, hence led to the development of new results-based assessment tools.

The Schools Division of Cauayan City was dubbed as the Ideal City of the North, and now the SMART City of the North innovatively growing to cope with the demand of time towards the Fourth Industrial Revolution (FIRe). The shift of focus from access to quality this year, enthused the SDO Cauayan City readjust Basic Educational Development Plan detouring Annual Implementation Plan Work and Financial Plan into programs, projects and activities targeting quality instruction focusing on the learning outcomes.

To realize the said goal, the proponent conceptualized a Project INSPIRE (Intensifying Nurturing Supervisory Partnership of Instructional leaders for Relevance and Excellence) to intensify supervision of instruction, nurture instructional leaders, supervise skills in planning, monitoring, conferencing and analyzing performance, strengthen school-community relationship, and establish meaningfulness of instruction. This project aims at offering curricula responsive to the uniqueness of learner excellently; providing them the appropriate learning opportunities and options amid meagre resources; networking with the civic-spirited stakeholders and community people for a sustainable support beyond expectation; and provision of avenue for teachers’ up skilling and reskilling for content, pedagogy and technical aspects more than the minimum standards.

With the aim of continual improvement, the proponent would like to assess the extent of implementation of the PROJECT. This is to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the project and the challenges encountered by the implementers so as to improve the delivery. Furthermore, the result of this study will contribute to the improvement of instructional leaders’ quality. Thus, refining learning outcomes and promoting learning and growth among learners.

Research Questions

Generally, this research study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of Project INSPIRE (Intensifying Nurturing Supervisory Partnership of Instructional leaders for Relevance and Excellence) in the Schools Division of Cauayan City which serve as a basis for continual improvement.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex;
 - 1.2. Position; and
 - 1.3. Years of Service in the current position?

2. What is the extent of implementation of the Project INSPIRE in terms of:
 - 1.1. Purpose/Objectives
 - 1.2. Instructional Supervision of Education Program Supervisors
 - 1.3. Instructional Supervision of School Heads
3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of Instructional Supervision of Education Program Supervisors when school heads are grouped according to sex, position, years in service?
4. Is there a significant difference on the extent of Instructional Supervision of School Heads when teachers are grouped according to sex, position, years in service?
5. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of Project INSPIRE?
6. What are the strengths of the Project INSPIRE?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed mixed-method both quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative method particularly the descriptive research design was used since its purpose is to obtain facts regarding the respondents' demographics such as sex, position and years of service, assess the extent of implementation of the following programs under the Project Inspire, and the significant difference on the extent of implementation of the Project INSPIRE when respondents are grouped according to their profile variables.

On the other hand, qualitative method through phenomenological research design was also be applied to determine the challenges encountered by the respondents in the implementation of Project INSPIRE, the strengths and weaknesses of the different programs under the project, and the proposed intervention to better the implementation of the project. Since the goal of the study is to assess the extent of implementation of Project INSPIRE particularly the instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors and School Heads, then the most appropriate respondents of this study are the school heads and teachers. School heads assessed the Education Program Supervisors while the Teachers evaluated the School Heads as to the implementation of the project. All school heads of 79 elementary and secondary schools in SDO Cauayan City were considered as respondents.

Meanwhile, to select teacher-respondents, the researcher made use of the 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error and then stratified random sampling was applied to get the respondents per school. There were 253 Elementary Teachers, 109 Senior High School Teachers, and 193 Junior High School Teachers who served as respondents of the study. To facilitate the collection of data, questionnaire and interview were utilized. The researcher made use of the frequency and percentage count, mean rating, t-test, ANOVA, and coding and thematic analysis in treating the data gathered.

RESULTS

Part I. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1

Distribution of School Heads According to their Profile

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	49.37
Female	40	50.63
Total	79	100

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher In-Charge	19	24.05
Head Teacher 1	8	10.13
Head Teacher 3	15	18.99
Principal 1	12	15.19
Principal 2	14	17.72
Principal 3	7	8.86
Principal 4	4	5.06
Total	79	100

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	4	5.06
6-10 years	7	8.86
11-15 years	15	18.98
16-20 years	7	8.86

Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
21-25 years	13	16.46
26-30 years	21	26.58
31years and above	12	15.20
Total	79	100

Table 1 shows the profile of the school heads. It can be gleaned that there are 40 female school heads or 50.63% and 39 male school heads with a percentage of 49.37. This implies that school heads in terms of age is almost equal in number.

In terms of position/designation, there are 19 or 24.05% Teacher In-Charge, 15 or 18.99% Head Teacher III, 14 or 17.72% Principal II, 12 or 15.19% Principal I, 8 or 10.13% Head Teacher I, 7 or 8.86% Principal III, and 4 or 5.06% Principal IV. This suggests that majority of the school heads are designated Teacher In-Charge.

Lastly, as reflected, majority (21 or 26.58%) of the school heads already rendered 26-30 years. Fifteen (15) or 18.98% of them are in the service for 11-15 years and 13 or 16.46% render 21-25 years. Moreover, there are 12 or 15.20% of them who render 31 years and above and there are 7 or 8.86% who have rendered 16-20 years and 6-10 years respectively. Meanwhile, there are 4 or 5.06% of the school heads who render 1-5

years. This suggests that majority of the school heads are in the service for 26-30 years already.

Table 2

Distribution of School Heads According to their Profile

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	153	27.57
Female	402	72.43
Total	555	100
Position	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher 1	79	14.23
Teacher 2	62	11.17
Teacher 3	350	63.06
Master Teacher 1	50	9.01
Master Teacher 2	6	1.08
Master Teacher 3	1	0.18
SPET-1	2	0.36
SST-1	5	0.90
Total	555	100
Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
Below 1 year	41	7.39
1-5 years	282	50.81
6-10 years	113	20.36
11-15 years	65	11.71
Years in Service	Frequency	Percentage
16 years and above	54	9.73
Total	555	100

Table 2 shows the profile of the teachers. It can be deduced from the figure that there are 402 or 72.43% female teacher-respondents and 153 or 27.57% male teacher-respondents. This infers that teacher-respondents are predominated by female teachers.

In terms of position of the teachers, it displays that most of the teacher-respondents (350 or 63.06%) Teacher III. Meanwhile, there is only 1 or 0.18% Master Teacher respondent. This deduces that teacher-respondents are outweighed by Teacher III position.

As regards their years in service, majority (282 or 50.81%) of the them are in the service for 1-5 years. One hundred thirteen (113) or 20.36% are in the service for 6-10 years and 65 or 11.71% render 11-15 years. Moreover, there are 54 or 9.73% of them who render 16 years and above and lastly, there are 41 or 7.39% who render below 1 year. This supposes that majority of the teachers are in the service for 1-5 years.

Part II. Extent of Implementation of the Project INSPIRE

1.1 Purpose

Table 3

Extent of Implementation of the Project INSPIRE as to its Purpose/Objectives

<i>The project:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. intensifies supervision of instruction and helps instructional leaders reinforce and enhance teaching practices.	4.61	Very Great Extent
2. seeks to encourage activity, innovativeness, integrity and productivity in leading and supervising instructions.	4.68	Very Great Extent
3. showcases the best-learning focused practices among schools, instructional leaders and teachers.	4.64	Very Great Extent
4. creates a culture of excellence and partnership in making authentic learning happen in the lives of school learners.	4.63	Very Great Extent
5. establishes functional and purposive supervisory processes to address challenge of quality basic education.	4.63	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.64	Very Great Extent

As can be seen in Table 1, the Project INSPIRE is fully implemented as to its purpose or objectives with an average mean rating of 4.64 or verbally described as “Very Great Extent” This indicates that the program really: intensifies supervision of instruction, nurtures instructional leaders; supervises skills in planning, monitoring, conferencing and analyzing performance; strengthens school-community relationship; and establishes meaningfulness of instruction. This is a clear manifestation that the Schools Division of Cauayan City is one with the DepEd’s Education Reform of targeting quality instruction focusing on the learning outcomes.

1.2 Instructional Supervision of Education Program Supervisors

Table 4

Instructional Supervision of Educational Program Supervisors in terms of Supporting Curriculum Management & Implementation

<i>The Education Program Supervisors:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. lead in designing and managing responsive support for curriculum implementation through efficient and	4.67	Very Great Extent

effective programs, projects, and activities aligned with curriculum standards		
2. lead colleagues/schools heads in innovating strategies to support curriculum contextualization	4.53	Very Great Extent
3. model exemplary practices in providing support for learning resource management in the division/district/school and learning centers.	4.60	Very Great Extent
4. show exemplary leadership skills in applying a wide range of intervention strategies based on results of learning outcomes assessment to support the division/districts/schools and learning centers.	4.50	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.58	Very Great Extent

Table 1 reflects that the instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors in supporting curriculum management and implementation is implemented to a very great extent with an average mean rating of 4.58.

This only implies that the Education Program Supervisors of SDO Cauayan City play their vital role in enhancing the management and delivery of the basic education curriculum particularly in taking the lead in designing and managing responsive support for curriculum implementation through efficient and effective programs, projects, and activities aligned with curriculum standards, thus, contributing to the realization of the department's goal and objectives.

Table 5

Instructional Supervision of Educational Program Supervisors in terms of Strengthening Shared Accountability

<i>The Education Program Supervisors:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. model exemplary skills in the provision of technical assistance by designing and implementing responsive interventions based on quality assurance and monitoring and evaluation results.	4.60	Very Great Extent
2. share best practice in the provision of enhanced support in the management of disaster preparedness, mitigation and resiliency to ensure delivery of basic education.	4.36	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.48	Very Great Extent

Table 3 shows the that the instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors in terms of strengthening shared accountability. As indicated, the EPSs strengthens shared accountability to a very great extent with an average mean rating of 4.48 as manifested by modelling of exemplary skills in the provision of technical

assistance and sharing of best practices in the provision of enhanced support in the management of disaster preparedness, mitigation, and resiliency.

As stipulated in the job summary for Education Program Supervisors, they shall provide technical support in the full implementation of the articulated basic education curriculum for a subject area and the development of learning resource materials to suit the conditions and context of the locality. Furthermore, they shall provide technical assistance to the Schools in curriculum implementation, instructional supervision and learning materials development and quality assurance.

Table 6

Instructional Supervision of Educational Program Supervisors in terms of Fostering a Culture of Continuous Improvement

<i>The Education Program Supervisors:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. lead colleagues/school heads in developing a compendium of effective and efficient instructional leadership support strategies to address the identified priority needs of the division/districts/schools and learning centers.	4.68	Very Great Extent
<i>The Education Program Supervisors:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
2. exhibit best practice in applying technology-based innovations including ICT to strengthen shared accountability and foster a culture of continuous improvement	4.02	Great Extent
3. exhibit exemplary skills in institutionalizing communities of practice for continuous improvement in the delivery of basic education services.	4.50	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.40	Very Great Extent

The extent of implementation of instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors in terms of fostering a culture of continuous improvement is indicated in Table 4. It can be inferred that EPSs lead colleagues/school heads in developing a compendium of effective and efficient instructional leadership support strategies (4.68) and exhibit exemplary skills in institutionalizing communities of practice for continuous improvement in the delivery of basic education services (4.50) to a very great extent. Meanwhile, they exhibit best practice in applying technology-based innovations including ICT (4.02) to a great extent.

This only reveals that supervisors really identify opportunities to reduce waste and streamline work. They find opportunities to execute processes more effectively and get

more from less and to drive sustainable and long-term results. However, application of technology-based innovations shall be strengthened.

Table 7

Instructional Supervision of Educational Program Supervisors in terms of Developing Self and Others

<i>The Education Program Supervisors:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. model exemplary practices in the delivery of different learning and development interventions to support division/district/school and/or learning centers.	4.42	Very Great Extent
2. lead reforms in enhancing personal and professional development programs based on in-depth knowledge and understanding of the Philippine Professional Standards for Supervisors	4.35	Very Great Extent
3. share best practices in providing enhanced support in the implementation of rewards and recognition mechanisms to acknowledge the outstanding performance of personnel.	4.12	Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.30	Very Great Extent

Table 5 illustrates the extent of implementation of instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors in terms of developing self and others.

As shown in the above table, EPSs model exemplary practices in the delivery of different learning and development interventions (4.42) and lead reforms in enhancing personal and professional development programs based on in-depth knowledge and understanding of the Philippine Professional Standards for Supervisors (4.35) to a very great extent. Meanwhile, they share best practices in providing enhanced support in the implementation of rewards and recognition mechanisms to acknowledge the outstanding performance of personnel (4.02) to a great extent.

1.3 Instructional Supervision of School Heads

Table 8

Instructional Supervision of School Heads in terms of Leading Strategically

<i>The School Heads:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. serve as a role model in the school and the wider school community in embodying the DepEd vision, mission, and core values to sustain shared understanding and alignment of	4.69	Very Great Extent

school policies, programs, projects, and activities.

2. share the school's best practices in the development and implementation of school plans aligned with institutional goals and policies. 4.67 Very Great Extent

3. lead in institutionalization of effective monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement. 4.02 Great Extent

Average Mean Rating 4.46 Very Great Extent

As can be seen in Table 1, the school heads serve as a role model in the school and the wider school community in embodying the DepEd vision, mission, and core values (4.69) and share the school's best practices in the development and implementation of school plans aligned with institutional goals and policies (4.67) to a very great extent. On the other hand, they lead in institutionalization of effective monitoring and evaluation processes and tools to promote learner achievement (4.02) to a great extent.

The result infers that school heads possess strategic leadership skills in achieving goals and drive performance among teachers. Additionally, they have the skills to handle complexity, bridge boundaries, and shape organizational culture for success. However, effective monitoring and evaluation processes must be strengthened by the school heads in order to promote optimum learning outcomes.

Table 9

Instructional Supervision of School Heads in terms of Managing School Operations and Resources

<i>The School Heads:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. exhibit best practice in managing school data and information using technology, including ICT, to ensure efficient and effective school operations.	4.63	Very Great Extent
2. create and implement a checking mechanism to sustain efficient and effective management of finances while adhering consistently to policies, guidelines and issuances in allocation, procurement, disbursement and liquidation aligned to the school plan.	4.67	Very Great Extent

3. systematize processes in managing school facilities and equipment in adherence to policies, guidelines and issuances on acquisition, recording, utilization, repair, and maintenance, storage and disposal.	4.64	Very Great Extent
4. empower school personnel in sustaining effective management of staff in adherence to laws, policies, guidelines, and issuances based on the needs of the school.	4.66	Very Great Extent
5. institutionalize the effective management of school safety for disaster preparedness, mitigation, and resiliency to sustain continuous delivery of instruction.	4.62	Very Great Extent
6. empower school personnel in managing emerging opportunities and challenges to ensure equality and equity in addressing the needs of learners, school personnel and other stakeholders.	4.69	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.65	Very Great Extent

Table 7 reflects that the instructional supervision of School Heads in managing school operations and resources is implemented to a very great extent with an average mean rating of 4.65.

As an implication, school heads exhibit best practice in managing school data and information using technology, including ICT, create and implement a checking mechanism to sustain efficient and effective management of finances, systematize processes in managing school facilities and equipment, empower school personnel in sustaining effective management, institutionalize the effective management of school safety for disaster preparedness, mitigation, and resiliency, and empower school personnel in managing emerging opportunities and challenges.

Table 10

Instructional Supervision of School Heads in terms of Focusing on Teaching and Learning

<i>The School Heads:</i>	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. share exemplary practice in the review, contextualization and implementation of learning standards to effectively assist teachers in making the curriculum relevant for learners.	4.60	Very Great Extent
2. exhibit best practice in providing technical assistance to teachers for them to develop exemplary practices consistent with teaching standards and pedagogies within and across learning areas.	4.63	Very Great Extent

3. exhibit exemplary skills in effectively using validated feedback obtained from learners, parents, and other stakeholders to help teachers improve their performance.	4.61	Very Great Extent
4. lead initiatives on the innovative use of learning assessment tools, strategies and results consistent with curriculum requirements to ensure accountability in achieving higher learning outcomes.	4.63	Very Great Extent
5. empower the wider school community in promoting and sustaining a learner-friendly, inclusive and healthy learning environment.	4.63	Very Great Extent
6. lead concerted efforts among stakeholders to develop and implement effective learner discipline policies to support student growth and whole school improvements.	4.65	Very Great Extent
Average Mean Rating	4.63	Very Great Extent

Table 8 presents that the instructional supervision of School Heads in focusing on teaching and learning is implemented to a very great extent with an average mean rating of 4.63.

This only shows that school heads recognize the role of stakeholders in developing and implementing effective learner discipline policies, take the lead initiatives on the innovative use of learning assessment tools and strategies, exhibit best practice in providing technical assistance to teachers, exhibit exemplary skills in effectively using validated feedback, and share exemplary practice in the review, contextualization and implementation of learning standards.

Table 11

Instructional Supervision of School Heads in terms of Developing Self and Others

The School Heads	Mean Rating	Verbal Description
1. exhibit exemplary practice in the efficient and effective implementation of the performance management system to ensure career advancement for individual school personnel.	4.65	Very Great Extent
2. model exemplary practice in the implementation of professional development initiatives to enhance strengths and address performance gaps among school personnel.	4.64	Very Great Extent
3. empower individuals and teams to consistently perform leadership roles and responsibilities in achieving school goals.	4.66	Very Great Extent
4. institutionalize the implementation of the school rewards system with support from the	4.10	Great Extent

wider school community in recognizing and motivating learners, school personnel, and other stakeholders.

Average Mean Rating	4.51	Very Great Extent
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Table 9 presents that the instructional supervision of School Heads in developing self and others is implemented to a very great extent with an average mean rating of 4.51.

School heads, as implied by the result, empower their colleagues to consistently perform leadership roles and responsibilities in achieving their goals. They also exhibit exemplary practice in the efficient and effective implementation of the performance management system and model exemplary practice in the implementation of professional development.

Nevertheless, school heads shall fortify the implementation of the school rewards system with support from the wider school community in recognizing and motivating learners, school personnel, and other stakeholders.

Part III. Test on Significant Difference

Table 12

Significant Difference on the Extent of Instructional Supervision of Education Program Supervisors when School Heads are grouped according to their profile variables

Variables	Computed t/f	P value @ 0.05	Result	Decision
Extent of Supervision of EPS vs. Sex	0.287348	.78035	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Extent of Supervision of EPS vs. Position	0.73668	.18554	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Extent of Supervision of EPS vs. Years in Service	7.05505	.000753	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 10 presents the test on significant difference on the extent of instructional supervision of Education Program Supervisors when school heads are grouped according to their profile variables. As reflected in the table, among the three (3) profile variables only years in service has significant difference with a probability value of .000753 which is less than the significance level @ 0.05. It means that the extent of instructional

supervision of the supervisors vary depending on the years of service of school heads. As reveal in the statistical result, school heads with 1-5 years of service need more supervision and guidance.

Extensive technical support or assistance must be extended to school heads who are new in the position as to the full implementation of the articulated basic education curriculum for a subject area and the development of learning resource materials to suit the conditions and context of the locality.

Moreover, the extent of instructional supervision given by the supervisors when school heads are grouped according to sex and position doesn't vary. Hence, these are not predictor variables.

Table 13

Significant Difference on the Extent of Instructional Supervision of School Heads when Teachers are grouped according to their profile variables

Variables	Computed t/f	P value @ 0.05	Remark	Decision
Extent of Supervision of School Heads vs. Sex	2.05601	.10252	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Extent of Supervision of School Heads vs. Position	8.23212	.001617	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Extent of Supervision of School Heads vs. Years in Service	4.999	.002024	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 11 reflects the test on significant difference on the extent of instructional supervision of School Heads when teacher-respondents are grouped according to their profile variables. As indicated, two of the three (3) profile variables have significant different which include the position and years in service. As to the position, the computed p value of .001617 is less than the level of significance (0.05) which means that the the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is significant. As regard to the other variable (years in service), the p value of .002024 is less than the level of significance which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Additionally, the extent of instructional supervision given by the school heads when teachers are grouped according to sex doesn't vary. Hence, this is not a predictor variable.

Part IV. Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in the Implementation of Project INSPIRE

The following are the identified themes based on the answer conducted among the respondents on the challenges they have encountered in the implementation of the said project.

Theme 1: Covid-19 Pandemic

As reflected in their answers, respondents agreed that the health crisis (Covid-19 Pandemic) deters the implementation of the Project INSPIRE. This somehow affects the instructional leaders in intensifying supervision of instruction, enhancing teaching practices, encouraging activity, innovativeness, integrity and productivity in leading and supervising instructions, creating a culture of excellence and partnership, and establishing functional and purposive supervisory processes.

Respondent J said that:

“Due to the pandemic that we are encountering, it is very hard for us to reach out stakeholders and learners. The lack of communication and participation hinders us on the aspect of school improvement and learners’ development.”

Respondent L added:

“The stakeholders and the school had a hard time in dealing with the changes brought by the new normal. The difficulty of communication hampers the development of some of the projects. The pandemic somehow affects the development of schools and the partnership from stakeholders.”

Respondent O added:

“In the advent of the health crisis, there was limited provision of face-to-face technical assistance from the supervisors but online modalities to cope up with the challenges.”

Theme 2: Multiple Tasks of School Heads

As revealed by the respondents, the multiple tasks of school heads could also affect his/her instructional supervision.

Respondent M mentioned that:

“Some school heads, if not all, play multiple roles, duties, and responsibilities which affect the implementation of the project especially in the provision of instructional supervision and technical assistance among teachers and other staff.”

Theme 3: Qualification/Capacity of School Heads

As mentioned by the respondents, school heads or instructional leaders will not be able to carry out instructional supervision and evaluation effectively if he/she is not well qualified and trained; a sound up-to-date knowledge of the subject matter, a good organizing skill, and ready to accept teacher's idea and interest.

Supervisors need continuous and sufficient training to carry out their responsibility effectively. Training programs of supervisors aimed at providing necessary skills for supervisors and make them better equipped at doing their job.

Theme 4: Unequal Opportunity for Teachers

Unequal opportunity for teachers especially in medium to large school category could also affect the instructional supervision of school heads where provision of technical assistance and guidance is given to selected few.

Respondent C revealed that:

“Unequal opportunity for teachers due to large number affects the effective implementation of the Project INSPIRE.”

Theme 5: Perception/Attitude of Teachers Towards Instructional Supervision

The improvement of the teaching-learning process is dependent upon teacher attitudes towards supervision. Unless teachers perceive supervision as a process of promoting professional growth and student learning, the supervisory exercise will not have the desired effect.

Respondent D revealed that:

“I strongly believe that attitude/perception of the school heads and teachers on the acceptance of change or challenge has an impact to the implementation of the Project INSPIRE. Great implementation always redounds to the positive attitude of both.”

Part V. Strengths of Project INSPIRE

The following are the identified themes based on the answers given by the respondents on the strengths of Project INSPIRE.

Theme 1: Intensifies Supervision and Transforms Instructional Leaders

As revealed by the respondents, Project INSPIRE can be a great platform in advocating effective teaching by providing clarity and support for teachers as well as procuring the necessary resources to maximize teaching effectiveness. This can also

empower instructional leaders in providing meaningful feedback and direction to teachers that can have a profound effect on the learning outcomes.

Respondents A revealed that:

“It nurtures partnership of instructional leaders for relevance and excellence.”

Theme 2: Strengthens Partnership

One of the generated themes is strengthening partnership through Project INSPIRE. They believe that the quality delivery of instruction is largely dependent on partnership. Moreover, through the said project partnership can enrich educational experiences for students, schools, and the community.

Respondent O revealed that:

“Project Inspire can build partnership among stakeholders which in return can contribute to the development of the school and the learners.”

Respondent B said that:

“It contributes to the development of learners through establishing connections with stakeholders in creating collaborative actions.”

Theme 3: Manages Instructional Program

Majority of the respondents mentioned that the Project INSPIRE can help manage instructional program in terms of supervising and evaluating instructions, coordinating curriculum, and monitoring students' development. Managing the instructional program requires the school head's active participation in stimulating, supervising, guiding, and monitoring teaching and learning in the school. Additionally, they have mentioned that the school head must possess expertise as well as commitment in the school's instruction and curriculum.

Respondent S stated that:

“Through this project we'll be able to evaluate the effectiveness of our instructions which help us improve in terms of elevating the performance of our learners.”

Respondent F stated that:

“The enhancement of the teaching process is basically geared towards the development of learners, hence, by enhancing the supervision of instruction, teachers are aiming to apply their learnings in executing lessons.”

Theme 4: Promotes Learning Management

One of the generated themes on the strengths of the Project INSPIRE based on the responses is the promotion of learning management through the following: promoting quality teaching; supervising and evaluating learning; allocating and protecting instructional period; coordinating curriculum; and monitoring students' progress.

Respondents C revealed that:

"I think the project inspire contribute to the development of the learners through various exposure activity, goals, and diverse learning and empowerment through great leadership."

Respondent D revealed that:

"There are many ways this project contributes to the development of the learners. One of which is that they can create culture of excellence in making authentic learning happen in the lives of every learner. Also, it exhibits exemplary skills in effectively using validated feedback coming from the learners, parents and other stakeholders to help teachers improve their performance."

Respondent S stated that:

"The learners being the end beneficiary of all these would surely gain. The teachers through the motivation and guidance of school head and other leaders are now working beyond limits---para sa bata, para sa bayan."

DISCUSSION

I. Profile of the Respondents

The demographic distribution of the school heads reveals a relatively balanced representation of males and females, suggesting equitable leadership participation across sexes. Their positions vary, with many serving in mid-level or entry-level leadership roles such as Teacher In-Charge or Head Teacher, reflecting the diverse pathways through which instructional leadership is exercised within schools. The wide range of years in service—from newly appointed to highly seasoned administrators—indicates a leadership workforce composed of individuals with differentiated levels of experience. This mix of tenure is significant because, as Eroles (2014) emphasizes, the effectiveness of supervision and decision-making often evolves with accumulated experience. Similarly, Chen (2018) notes that leadership capacity is shaped by exposure to varied instructional contexts, indicating that a diverse leadership profile can strengthen the overall management of schools.

The teacher-respondents also reflect a similar trend of gender imbalance commonly seen in the teaching profession, with more female teachers participating in the workforce. Their positions show a strong concentration in the Teacher III level, suggesting that many have reached a stage of career maturity where they are expected to carry greater instructional responsibilities. The distribution of years in service indicates that a large portion of teachers are relatively new to the profession, which may influence the type of supervision, mentoring, and professional development they require. Shackman (2018) underscores that the level of teacher experience significantly affects readiness for instructional innovation and responsiveness to supervision. Therefore, the demographic profile of both school heads and teachers provides important context for understanding the dynamics of instructional supervision within the division, especially as varying levels of experience shape how support, guidance, and leadership interventions are received and implemented.

II. Extent of Implementation of the Project INSPIRE

The findings show that Project INSPIRE is implemented extensively, demonstrating strong alignment with the national call for instructional reforms and quality education under *Sulong EduKalidad* (2020). The project successfully fulfills its purpose of strengthening supervision, enriching instructional practices, and building a culture of excellence and shared responsibility among educators. This is consistent with Esa et al. (2017), who emphasize that well-structured instructional systems enhance teacher performance and student outcomes. The results reflect that Cauayan City's initiatives uphold DepEd Order No. 230, s. 1999, which mandates clear, functional, and learner-centered supervisory processes. Moreover, the emphasis on collaboration and school-community partnerships resonates with the perspective of the National Center for Education Statistics (2018), which underscores shared accountability as a key driver of improved school performance.

In terms of instructional supervision by Education Program Supervisors (EPS), the project demonstrates strong implementation in curriculum management, shared accountability, continuous improvement, and professional development. EPSs perform their mandated roles by ensuring responsive curriculum support, leading instructional innovations, and providing technical assistance, affirming the supervisory responsibilities outlined in *Principal's Responsibilities* (2015) and Kabiro (2013). Their ability to cultivate improvement processes and communities of practice aligns with Ubben's (2011) view that effective supervision builds capacity and ensures instructional coherence. Although technology integration was slightly less emphasized, the recognized potential of ICT in streamlining instruction and improving access to learning resources supports the Asian Development Bank (2009), which stresses the transformative power of digital tools in enhancing learning opportunities and reducing educational gaps.

The instructional supervision of school heads is similarly strong across strategic leadership, resource management, teaching and learning, and the development of personnel. School heads demonstrate effective leadership by modeling core values, aligning school programs with institutional goals, and sustaining inclusive and learner-

centered environments—an expectation consistent with Barzallo (2020) and Patzer (2020), who note that strong school leadership greatly influences school climate and learner outcomes. Their effective management of operations, resources, and staff mirrors DepEd standards and highlights their role in creating safe, efficient, and equitable learning spaces. However, the need to further strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and recognition systems suggests that continuous refinement is essential for sustaining motivation and ensuring long-term improvement. Overall, the results affirm that Project INSPIRE has successfully enhanced supervisory performance, contributing to improved instructional quality and reinforcing the national agenda for educational excellence.

III. Test of Significant Difference on the Extent of Instructional Supervision of Education Program Supervisors when School Heads are grouped according to their profile variables

The results of the analysis indicate that the instructional supervision provided by Education Program Supervisors differs depending on the years of service of school heads. This suggests that newer school leaders require more support, technical assistance, and guidance as they adjust to their supervisory and instructional roles. This aligns with Eroles (2014), who emphasized that leadership effectiveness develops over time and that newly appointed administrators often require structured supervision as they build experience in curriculum management and instructional leadership. Chen (2018) similarly noted that leadership readiness and competence evolve gradually, reinforcing the need for targeted support to foster confidence and capability among less experienced school heads. Meanwhile, the findings show that sex and position do not influence the level of supervision required, indicating that these characteristics do not predict variations in supervisory needs.

In addition, the instructional supervision provided by school heads varies among teachers depending on their position and length of service. This suggests that teachers at different stages of their careers require different levels and types of instructional support. Shackman (2018) notes that employee experience levels influence how they interpret feedback and supervision, which may explain why instructional guidance needs differ between novice and more seasoned teachers. Consistent with Chen's (2018) view on differentiated leadership practices, this finding highlights the importance of tailoring supervisory approaches based on teachers' experience and professional roles to enhance teaching performance. Similar to the results for school heads, the variable of sex did not produce differences in supervision, indicating that demographic characteristics are less relevant than professional experience in predicting supervisory needs.

IV. Challenges Encountered by the Respondents in the Implementation of Project INSPIRE

The findings reveal that the implementation of Project INSPIRE is shaped by several challenges that stem from both external conditions and internal organizational factors. The Covid-19 pandemic emerged as a major obstacle, disrupting communication,

limiting supervisory interactions, and slowing school improvement efforts. This aligns with Merga (2007), who emphasized that crises often weaken institutional collaboration and reduce stakeholder participation. Likewise, the multiple responsibilities carried by school heads created strain on their ability to consistently provide instructional supervision. Weerakon (2017) supports this observation, noting that excessive administrative workload tends to diminish leaders' capacity to focus on professional support and teaching quality. These circumstances illustrate how environmental pressures and work demands can significantly affect the consistency and depth of supervision.

Other challenges were rooted in the capacity and readiness of instructional leaders, along with perceptions and attitudes of teachers toward supervision. Respondents highlighted the importance of proper training, adequate preparation, and equitable opportunities for all teachers to receive guidance—factors also emphasized by Eroles (2014), who argued that supervisory effectiveness depends on competence, fairness, and support structures. Negative perceptions or resistance toward supervision were also seen as barriers, reinforcing Durlak's (2011) assertion that positive attitudes and supportive relationships are essential for successful program implementation. Together, these findings show that while Project INSPIRE has strong potential, its success relies heavily on adequately prepared leaders, equitable supervisory practices, and a positive school climate that encourages openness and collaboration.

V. Strengths of Project INSPIRE

The results highlight that Project INSPIRE strengthens instructional leadership by promoting deeper supervision, clearer guidance, and more meaningful support for teachers. Respondents emphasized that the project empowers instructional leaders to provide relevant feedback and foster a shared commitment to excellence. This reflects the view of Domitrovich and Greenberg (2000), who argue that well-designed school initiatives enhance implementation quality by improving the competence and confidence of leaders. The project also fosters partnerships among stakeholders, reinforcing the idea that collaborative relationships significantly enrich educational experiences. Barzallo (2017) similarly noted that strong school–community partnerships contribute to improved learning environments by integrating shared responsibility and collective action.

Furthermore, respondents recognized that Project INSPIRE enhances the management of instructional programs by enabling school heads to coordinate curriculum, monitor student progress, and guide teachers more effectively. This aligns with Chen's (2018) assertion that leadership practices focused on supervision and curriculum coordination contribute to better teaching performance and learner outcomes. The project also promotes strong learning management practices, allowing teachers to provide quality instruction while ensuring that students receive consistent support. Kabiro (2015) emphasized that effective instructional leadership creates a culture of excellence by continuously using feedback and evidence-based strategies to improve teaching. Overall, the results show that Project INSPIRE strengthens leadership capacity, deepens collaboration, and directly supports the continuous development of teachers and learners.

Conclusions

In light of the presented findings, the following conclusions have been derived:

The demographic profile of school heads and teachers indicates a balanced mix of genders, positions, and years of service, highlighting diversity in leadership experience and teaching tenure. This variety suggests that the division has a combination of seasoned and relatively new educators, which can influence how supervision, guidance, and professional development are delivered and received. Overall, understanding these characteristics provides valuable context for planning effective instructional support and fostering a responsive school environment.

The Project INSPIRE has been extensively implemented, effectively strengthening supervision, enhancing instructional practices, and fostering a culture of excellence and shared responsibility among educators. Both Education Program Supervisors and school heads demonstrate strong leadership and supervisory practices, ensuring responsive curriculum support, professional development, and effective management of school operations and resources. Overall, the project has significantly contributed to improving instructional quality, promoting collaboration, and reinforcing a learner-centered and high-performing educational environment.

Moreover, the instructional supervision needs vary according to the experience of both school heads and teachers, with newer leaders and less experienced teachers requiring more guidance, support, and targeted feedback. Differences in sex or position do not appear to influence supervisory requirements, emphasizing that professional experience and career stage are the key factors in determining the level and type of instructional support needed. These findings underscore the importance of tailoring supervision to individual experience levels to enhance leadership effectiveness and teaching performance.

In addition, the implementation of Project INSPIRE faces challenges arising from both external events and internal organizational factors. Disruptions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and the multiple responsibilities of school heads have limited consistent supervision and affected school improvement efforts. Additionally, the capacity and readiness of instructional leaders, along with teachers' attitudes toward supervision, influence the effectiveness of the project, highlighting the need for well-prepared leaders, equitable support, and a positive school environment to ensure successful implementation.

Furthermore, the Project INSPIRE effectively strengthens instructional leadership by providing clearer guidance, meaningful support, and opportunities for leaders to offer relevant feedback. The project also fosters collaboration among stakeholders, enhancing school–community partnerships and promoting shared responsibility for educational outcomes. Additionally, it improves the management of instructional programs and learning practices, supporting teachers in delivering quality instruction and contributing to the continuous development of both educators and learners.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations based In the findings of the study:

1. Provide regular and technical assistance for newly appointed school heads to help them adjust to supervisory and instructional responsibilities effectively.
2. Tailor instructional supervision and guidance according to teachers' years of experience and career stage to maximize professional growth and teaching performance.
3. Conduct regular training and development programs for both Education Program Supervisors and school heads to strengthen leadership skills, curriculum management, and instructional supervision.
4. Ensure all teachers receive consistent guidance and access to professional development, avoiding favoritism or selective support, especially in larger schools.
5. Encourage the use of ICT and digital tools to facilitate instructional supervision, curriculum monitoring, and communication, particularly in situations where face-to-face interactions are limited.
6. Establish regular monitoring and evaluation of instructional practices and supervision effectiveness, ensuring timely feedback and adjustments to support teaching and learning outcomes.
7. Reduce the non-instructional workload of school heads to allow more focus on supervision, instructional leadership, and teacher support.
8. Continue developing collaborative relationships with stakeholders to enhance shared responsibility, resource support, and overall school improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research will safeguard that the respondents give their voluntary assent and consent before participating. The researcher will clearly articulate the purpose, process, and potential risk of the study as well as give options on what to do in case a participant wants to discontinue their involvement, stating that there will be no effect on their employment status or any related negative implications.

To achieve confidentiality and anonymity, secured storages of the data obtained after the survey will be used, and supervision with utmost discretion will be adhered to. No personal names nor hospital identifiers will be linked to the outcome. Only codes or pseudonyms will be copied in the whole research process to ensure confidentiality. The experiment will abide by data protection laws too, namely, the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Ensuring the safe and secure environment for everybody involved is the utmost condition. The survey, therefore, will be designed not to harm the participants physically, emotionally, or professionally, and the means will be used to ensure that the participants are not subjected to any negative or retaliatory action because of involvement in the research.

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